

POLYMERIC COMPOSITES, PREPARED BY SOL-GEL METHOD, WITH SPATIAL GRADIENTS OF HYDROXYAPATITE BIOACTIVE SIGNALS

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ABSTRACT

Based on the bioactivity and biocompatibility of hydroxyapatite (HA) and good mechanical performance of poly- ϵ -caprolactone (PCL), the aim of this work was to define novel strategies to develop bioresorbable composite materials for bone repair and regeneration. This study describes the preparation and characterization of HA/PCL composite substrates by sol-gel and biomineralization methods. In particular, the proposed synthesis allows the improving the interaction between the ceramic and the polymer phases whereas the surface biomineralization through a bone-like apatite layer enable to enhance the bone cell recognition from cells.

Keywords: *Composite, Hydroxyapatite, Sol-gel, Biomineralization*

INTRODUCTION

Different shapes and sizes of bone defects caused by trauma, tumour and infections must be filled with suitable substances to promote bone repair. In each of these tissue engineering approaches, the degree of success likely depends on the properties of the substituting materials [1]. The most common bone substitutes used in clinic are autografts, allografts, polymers (PLLA, PMMA, PCL etc.) and ceramics such as dense and porous hydroxyapatite (HA), tricalcium phosphate ceramics and bioglass ceramic in the system of $\text{Na}_2\text{O-CaO-SiO}_2\text{-P}_2\text{O}_5$. But none of the materials presently available is entirely suitable for orthopaedic applications, each suffering specific disadvantages [2]. In fact, autografts are restricted by their donor bone supply, allografts might elicit an immunologic response in the human body, and some polymers as polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) would lead to local necrosis of tissue due to a great deal of heat released on the setting process [3]. A variety of calcium phosphates have been used for bone engineering applications. Hydroxyapatite and other calcium phosphates, e.g. tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP), are considered osteoconductive materials allowing new bone formation and have gained wide use as bone substitutes in the clinical area [4,5]. Especially, synthetic hydroxyapatite is known to be one of most important implantable materials due its biocompatibility, bioactivity and osteoconductivity coming from the analogy to the mineral components of natural bones, and is used as substitute material for human hard tissues. Although these materials can closely replicate the structure of human bone, the improvement of its mechanical properties is still very much desirable. The inherent brittleness and low tensile strength of HA materials confine their medical applications, such as repair of bone defects, bone augmentation, as well coatings for metallic implants [6,7]. Moreover, such bioactive

materials should spontaneously bond to and integrate with bone in the living body. Recently, much attention has been focused on HA/polymer composites, especially those containing biodegradable polymers. The polymeric parts are metabolized and excreted, and the ceramic constituents are assimilated in the body. The brittleness of HA ceramics is also improved by mixing with tough organic polymers [8]. Poly- ϵ -caprolactone (PCL) is one of the main polymer groups used in biomaterials research. It is a type of biodegradable polymer with good biocompatibility and the capacity for drug transport. Also it is relatively hydrophobic and has a slow degradation rate, ideal for use as bone substitutes and sustained release drug carriers [9-13]. Recently, different strategies have been developed to realize Hydroxyapatite/Polycaprolactone composites by physically blending [14]. The most significant problem occurring during the traditional blending process consists in a non-homogeneity distribution of ceramic phase in the polymeric matrix which dramatically reduces the bioactive potential of the composite. Sol-gel approaches have attracted much attention [15-18] because of the well-known inherent advantages of technique to generate glass, glass-ceramic and ceramics powders; these include: homogeneous molecular mixing, low processing temperature, the ability to generate nano-sized particles, bulk amorphous and thin films. There is considerable interest in organic-inorganic hybrid composite materials prepared via the sol-gel process [19-22]. The sol-gel approaches studied so far however have some shortcomings, most significantly, the use of either expensive alkoxide-based precursors or the need for several complicated steps to ensure complete dissolution of precursors to generate phase pure HA. A variety of organic polymers has been introduced into inorganic networks to afford the hybrid or composite materials with or without covalent bonds between the polymer and inorganic, components, respectively. In particular the presence of organic components modifies the morphology and physical properties of the sol-gel products. In fact, it is well known that the polymer matrix influences the formation of the HA nanocrystallites by specific organic-inorganic interactions [23,24] between components such as covalent bonds, ion-dipole or/and by complexation of Ca^{2+} with some functional groups from polymer.

The aim of this work is to develop novel HA/PCL composites by non-alkoxide-based sol-gel method at room temperature. The chemical synthesis of the HA powder by selected chemical solvents of the polymer defines a novel pathway to generate homogeneous composite materials preserving the microstructural features of HA crystals. The composite material was submitted to SBF treatment to investigate bioactivity activity through the formation of a layer consisting of bone-like apatite that is an essential condition for bioactive materials to achieve direct bonding with living bone. Therefore, the coating of a bone-like apatite layer onto organic polymers is an impressive candidate for the production of bioactive bone substitutes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Composite of HA/PCL (40/60w/w) was prepared by sol-gel method at room temperature. In particular, HA solution was prepared by using $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and P_2O_5 as precursors and ethanol was used as the solvent. In brief, the $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01mol; Sigma Aldrich, 99%) and P_2O_5 (0.003mol, Sigma Aldrich) were used with the molar ratio 10:3, which is the desiderated Ca/P ratio observed in hydroxyapatite and different solutions of Ca and P precursors were prepared in ethyl alcohol by stirring at room temperature for 30 minutes. NH_4OH was utilized to adjust the pH to 11 value.

After this step the precursor solutions were mixed to obtain HA solution. Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) pellets (Sigma Aldrich MW 65 kDa) were dissolved (20%w/w) in Chloroform by stirring for about 4 hours at 40°C. The HA solution was added into PCL solution (40/60 w/w) and the system transforms into a gel after 24hours. Fig.1 shows the flow chart of chemical synthesis of HA/PCL composite material. The gel system is the dried in an oven at 40°C in air for 3 days. HA/PCL composite material was soaked in SBF solution, at 37°C to 7 days, afterwards was incubated in 1.5SBF to 14 and 21 days. Taking in to account that the ratio of the exposed surface to the volume solution influences the reaction, a constant ratio was respected of 50mm² ml⁻¹ of solution. The SBF with ion composition nearly equal to blood plasma and an aqueous solution (1.5SBF) with ion concentration 1.5 times those of SBF were prepared by dissolving reagent grade salts of NaCl, NaHCO₃, Na₂SO₄, KCl, K₂HPO₄, MgCl₂•6H₂O, and CaCl₂•2H₂O in water and buffered at a pH value of 7.4 at 37°C with tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane ((CH₂OH)₃CNH₂) and 1M hydrochloric acid (HCl). This fluid is a metastable solution containing calcium and phosphate ions already supersaturated with respect to apatite. The concentrations of the ions were reported in table 1 [24]. The SBF solution was changed every 48 hours to ensure sufficient ion concentrations for mineral growth.

Ion	Blood plasma (mol/m³)	SBF (mol/m³)
Na⁺	142.0	142.0
K⁺	5.0	5.0
Mg²⁺	1.5	1.5
Ca²⁺	2.5	2.5
Cl⁻	103.0	147.8
HCO³⁻	27.0	4.2
HPO₄²⁻	1.0	1.0
SO₄²⁻	0.5	0.5

Table 1. Ion concentrations of blood plasma and Simulated Body Fluid (SBF)

Surface morphology of HA/PCL composite material was investigated by using a Leica Cambridge (Stereoscan S440) scanning electron microscope (Cambridge, UK). The material for SEM analysis was prepared by deposition of material onto one side of a double adhesive tape, which was stuck to an aluminium stub. The stub was then gold coated in an automatic sputter coater (EMSCOPE SC500) to a thickness of around 30nm at an accelerating potential of 20 kV. Elemental distribution analysis, particularly Ca and P, was carried out by an Energy-Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) using an Inca Energy 200 (Oxford Instruments, UK), which was directly connected to SEM. FITR spectra by Nicolet 5700 was used to study chemical interaction between inorganic and polymer phases in composite material.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The composite approach to combining bioactive ceramics and degradable polymers is a promising strategy to design and develop hard tissue regenerative materials. Among the number of biomedical composites developed thus far, HA/PCL composites have recently been examined by several groups and have been reported to be a potential candidate for hard tissue regeneration [25].

SEM micrographs show the presence of a microporosity characterized by average pore sizes of few microns able to regulate the nutrient transport and to support eventual vascularization. In particular, the SEM analysis of the composite material shows (Fig.2a) that the HA particles are spherical and no distinct orientation can be observed to be induced by the presence of ammonium nitrate. It does appear that the chemically synthesized HA is made up of very fine crystallites that are homogeneously distributed throughout the polymeric matrix. SEM shows an optimal dispersion of HA particles into PCL matrix, which partially cover them, so preventing a clear definition of particles boundaries. EDS analysis shows that the inorganic phase dispersed into polymeric matrix presents a Ca/P molar ratio typical of hydroxyapatite (Fig.2b). FTIR analysis on composite material illustrates a presence of symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching of the PO₄ group (at 1096, 1046, 963, 604 and 576 cm⁻¹), the stretching and vibrational modes of the OH groups at 3571-639 cm⁻¹ confirms the presence of HA phase in support of EDS analysis. Moreover, the FTIR studies show a presence of organic phase (PCL) with a peak at 1720 cm⁻¹ of carboxyl group and at 2867-2943 cm⁻¹ represent CH₂ group that move to 2868 and 2945 cm⁻¹ in composite material.

The bioactive potential of HA/PCL composite material was investigated by biomimetic approach in Simulated Body Fluid (SBF). Human body fluid and SBF contain calcium and phosphate ions that are already supersaturated with respect to apatite. However, these fluids do not spontaneously deposit apatite under normal conditions, due to high energy barrier for the apatite nucleation. In this case, the high SBF supersaturation degree as well as the contribution of substrates to induce heterogeneous nucleation of apatite are key issues for apatite formation on materials. Once apatite nuclei form, crystals of apatite grow spontaneously by consuming calcium and phosphate ions from the surrounding body fluid, which is already supersaturated with respect to apatite, to form a layer of bone-like apatite. Consequently, the apatite layer fully covers the surface [26]. From the findings described above, it can be said that apatite deposition from SBF onto materials is governed by: (a) the increase in the degree of supersaturation of SBF with respect to apatite; and (b) the ability of selective induction of crystal nucleation (heterogeneous nucleation) of apatite on the surface of materials. In this work the combination of two different treatments, by 1×SBF and 1.5SBF solutions, allow to guide the evolution of crystals formation. In particular, the proposed treatment consists of two steps (nucleation and growth) where the immersion of the material in SBF is induction period for apatite nucleation. Then, when the materials are soaked in another solution highly supersaturated with respect to the apatite, e.g. a solution (1.5SBF) with ion concentrations 1.5 times those of SBF, the apatite nuclei grow on the surface in situ by consuming the calcium and phosphate ions from the surrounding fluid [27]. As the period of the first treatment increases, 2 to 7 days, the number of apatite nuclei increases and hence a continuous apatite layer is formed during the second treatment. The formation of a layer of bone-like apatite on composite material in SBF solution has been confirmed by SEM micrograph and related EDS which indicate a Ca/P ratio around

1.67 (Fig.3). In SEM image is possible to see that the surface of the crystals was very rough and after 21 days immersion in SBF, a thick and dense mineral layer was formed on the specimen material.

The apatite coating can reduce fibrous encapsulation [27,28], promote bone in growth, enhance direct bone contact, and has also been shown to promote differentiation of bone mesenchymal stem cells along osteogenic lineage.

CONCLUSIONS

Biodegradable PCL/HA composite by sol-gel method at room temperature has been performed with success. Indeed, proposed technique allows obtaining bioactive composite materials with a wide spatial distribution of ceramic phase based on stoichiometric HA. Microstructural analysis indicates that the HA particles were distributed homogeneously within the PCL matrix, being in marked contrast to the conventional composite, in which the HA particles were severely agglomerated into micrometer-sized particles. The uniformly dispersed HA component improve the bioactive potential of composite material, in fact the addition of a continuous bone-like apatite coating by biomimetic process in SBF solution represents a promising strategy for the development of bioactive substrates for bone regeneration.

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Fig.1 Flow chart of chemical synthesis of HA/PCL composite material.

(a)

(b)

Fig.2: SEM images and EDAX spectrum of PCL/HA composite material.

Fig.3: SEM images (at different magnifications) and EDAX spectrum of PCL/HA composite material after 21 days immersion in SBF.